

Research Article

Psychological well-being in adolescents: examining the role of sibling rivalry

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Abstract

During adolescent development, it is not uncommon to encounter problems such as juvenile delinquency. Juvenile delinquency is a result of low levels of psychological well-being. One of the things that is a factor forming good psychological well-being in adolescents is the family environment. Problems that are often found in the family sphere are forms of parental support and adolescent egocentricity that tends to be high. If parents show rivalry and hostility in sibling relationships, it will have an impact on the emergence of negative experiences, in the form of sibling rivalry reactions. The purpose of this study was to examine whether sibling competition has a role in the psychological well-being of adolescents. Participants consisted of 147 grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso using purposive sampling. The scale of sibling competition and the scale of psychological well-being were constructed and through factor analysis tests to obtain a fit model as an instrument of this study. Regression analysis showed sibling competition played a significant role in psychological well-being with a contribution of 13.7%. The impact of sibling competition, both in positive and negative terms, has a link to psychological well-being. Thus, the hypothesis of this study can be proven and accepted.

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Introduction

In the period of human development, grade 10 students are the transition period between adolescence to adulthood. The age range of adolescent development lasts from the age of 10-12 years to the age of 18-21 years before entering early adulthood (Santrock, 2019a). During this transition period, Tangdilintin (2019) explained that adolescents tend to be labile because basically they still haven't found a grip on life. So that makes adolescents very vulnerable to being affected by positive and negative things.

Adolescence is often considered a critical period, where there are changing challenges, demands, and tasks transitioning from childhood to adulthood. Things related to this period of development are about mental, physical, and psychological functions (Santrock, 2019b). Those who are unable to adapt to their developmental tasks will tend to engage in maladaptive activities, such as the occurrence of juvenile delinquency (Murray et al., 2021)

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), it is known that there is an increase in juvenile delinquency cases every year. The number of juvenile delinquency cases in Indonesia reached 6325 cases in 2013. Similarly, the following year reached 7007 cases. Even in 2015 it could reach 7762 cases. The cases continue to grow to this day.

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Bondowoso is no exception, juvenile delinquency also occurs a lot, including in the environment of High School Students (SMA). This is evidenced by the raid activities carried out by the Civil Service Police Unit (SATPOL PP) Bondowoso Regency together with unit IV Protection of Women and Children Resort Police (PPA Polres) Bondowoso. As well as socialization was also carried out by the Adolescent Information and Counseling Center (PIK-R) TASMANIA under the supervision of the National Population and Family Planning Board (BKKBN) of Bondowoso Regency, Bondowoso Regency Health Office, and PPA Bondowoso Police.

This fact is an indicator that teenagers in Indonesia, especially in Bondowoso, still commit juvenile delinquency. Similar to Public Senior High School (SMAN) X Bondowoso, many cases of juvenile delinquency are also carried out by students. Based on the results of interviews with several teaching teachers and guidance teachers of SMAN X Bondowoso, data was obtained that juvenile delinquency in schools continues to increase every year. Juvenile delinquency is one of the focuses handled by the Guidance and Counseling (BK) of SMAN X Bondowoso. The school often collaborates with external parties such as psychologists, Bondowoso Regional Police, and SATPOL PP Bondowoso Regency as an effort to reduce the intensity of juvenile delinquency within the school.

Juvenile delinquency is one of the consequences of the low level of psychological well-being in adolescents (Coal, 2017). Akhtar (2009) explained that the critical period in adolescence will be passed well when adolescents have a good foundation of psychological well-being. In addition, Akhtar (2009) also explained that positive emotions, life satisfaction, happiness, and reduced negative behavior will appear when adolescents have good psychological well-being. Basically, psychological well-being can help increase positive emotions, build positive relationships with others, and adolescents can feel life satisfaction and happiness which has a role to reduce the risk of delinquency in adolescents (Akhtar & Boniwell, 2010).

Research by Ramadhani et al., (2016) produced an explanation that students with high psychological well-being can help them complete developmental tasks and challenges well, have a calm, happy outlook on life, and make it easier for them to overcome the problems faced. Similarly, Na'imah & Tanireja (2017) stated that a low level of psychological well-being in adolescents at school will tend to lead adolescents to experience serious social problems, including juvenile delinquency.

Psychological well-being is the ability of a person or individual to accept themselves, establish good relationships with others, be independent when dealing with the social environment, be able to have control with the external environment, establish life goals, and can maximize the potential that exists in themselves (Ryff, 2014). Here the role of psychological well-being is needed by adolescents so that juvenile delinquency acts are reduced. Muqhniiy & Amna (2016) stated that adolescents need high psychological well-being to improve good relationships with others and accept shortcomings and advantages in themselves.

Smith stated that the problem of psychological well-being in adolescents is an urgency that must get more attention because it is one of the main aspects in adolescent development at school (Pertiwi & Frieda, 2018). Adolescents who are still in school on average need good psychological well-being to optimize aspects of adolescent or student development and learning outcomes. The effect of improving the psychological well-being of adolescents in school can be a good main basis of adolescents themselves (Prabowo, 2016). Psychological well-being has an important role for students, especially in the world of education. The potential of students in school is more or less influenced by the psychological well-being of these students (Ryff, 2014).

The dimensions of psychological well-being based on Ryff (2014) are first the purpose in life, the beliefs possessed by individuals related to the purpose and meaning of life; secondly self-development, the ability to face stages of development, accept new experiences, and realize one's potential; third self-acceptance, acceptance of both positive and negative aspects in oneself; fourth independence, the ability to make good decisions in oneself; fifth positive relationships with others, having good interpersonal relationships; And finally is mastery of the environment, able to control the environment well. Then, factors that affect psychological well-being are age, culture, marital status,

socioeconomic status and social support (Wells, 2010). Wells (2010) also emphasizes that social support is a factor that greatly influences the level of psychological well-being of adolescents.

Social support from family, especially parents, is very impactful on the development of individual psychological well-being (Sarafino & Smith, 2017). This is also supported by the statement of Mami & Suharnan (2015) that parental support has an impact on the level of psychological well-being of a person. Less support from parents will cause disappointment in adolescents which will later affect the success of adolescents in achieving goals, especially academics.

But during their development, adolescents will spend more time with their friends, not with their family. Their egocentrics are also more inclined. According to Elkind, there are two egocentric components of adolescents, one of which is personal fable, which shows a sense of uniqueness and invincibility in adolescents (Santrock, 2019a). They will feel that no one can understand them, including family. Therefore, cooperation between parents and children is needed to fulfill the support from parents needed by children. Positive relationships formed from interactions between siblings are also social support from the family that must be considered. If parents show an attitude of competition and hostility in sibling relationships, this will have an impact on the emergence of negative experiences, in the form of competitive reactions between siblings (Papamichail & Bates, 2022).

Competition between siblings is a form of jealousy, competition, and hatred that arises in siblings (Shaffer & Kipp, 2014). According to VandenBos (2015), competition between siblings is defined as competition that occurs between siblings with the aim of getting appreciation, affection, recognition, as well as attention and self-esteem from their parents. The manifestation of sibling competition according to Goldstein & Naglieri (2011) can be regression, aggression, frustration, and always seeking attention. Sibling rivalry usually arises when one sibling feels that the love, affection, and appreciation given by parents is more inclined to the other sibling. This case is often found in the age range of 1-5 years. However, if not resolved properly, competition between siblings will reappear at the age of 12-18 years and can take the form of deviant and destructive behavior or referred to as the delayed effect (Masruroh & Ramadhana, 2016). This is also in accordance with the statement of Hou et al. (2020) if negative things that lead to sibling competition in children are not avoided, it will continue and affect the development process.

According to Shaffer & Kipp (2014), aspects of competition between siblings include jealousy, a form of disacceptance of the emergence of others which is considered to allow the sharing of affection from loved ones; resentment, an emotional reaction in the form of hostility caused by someone or something that is considered harmful; and competition, a state in which one person strives for something better than others (VandenBos, 2015).

Individuals with high levels of sibling competition have an influence on the emergence of self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and poor self-adjustment in school (Laeque et al., 2022). The opposite is evidenced in the research of Buist et al. (2013), which shows the results that individuals with a low level of sibling competition have a high sense of security and are able to adjust and have good prosocial behavior and emotional regulation. This is because the role of brothers is one of the factors for solving problems in the environment. Siblings play an important role in developmental and relational experiences that can also affect the quality of life that occurs during adolescence and young adulthood (Jensen et al., 2023).

Problems that occur between siblings can also affect a person's psychological well-being. This is evidenced through research conducted by Pertiwi & Frieda (2018), it was found that there is a relationship between sibling competition and psychological well-being in grade VII students of SMP Negeri 12 Semarang. Other studies on different subjects were also conducted by Fahmi & Handayani (2018) showing a relationship between sibling relationship dimensions, namely competition between siblings with psychological well-being in adolescents who have Down syndrome siblings. Stocker et al., (2019) also stated that there is a negative relationship between sibling competition and perceptions related to parental favoritism with psychological well-being in children, adolescents, and early adulthood. The results of Hasanah & Fitri's (2020) research also found the influence of sibling competition on the psychological well-being of high school students in West Jakarta. The authenticity of this study is based on research that has been done previously

which has similar objectives but was conducted on a different subject, namely grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso. Based on this, the research carried out can be accounted for its authenticity.

The purpose of this study was to determine the role of sibling competition on psychological well-being in grade 10 students of SMAN X in Bondowoso. Based on what was explained earlier, this study has a hypothesis in the form of a role between sibling competition and psychological well-being in grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso.

Method

The type of research used to prove the hypothesis is a quantitative approach with a correlational design which aims to prove whether the independent variable has a role in the dependent variable. In this study, the variables measured were sibling rivalry as the independent/free variable (variable X) and psychological well-being as the dependent/dependent variable (variable Y).

The population used in this study were 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso. Based on the data provided by the BK SMAN X Bondowoso there were 350 students and as many as 317 students who met the research criteria, namely having siblings. Based on the table of Isaac and Michael (Sugiyono, 2019) with this population, it was found that the sample size was 147 people with a significance level of 10%. The sampling technique used is *purposive sampling*. In carrying out this research, the authors used used trials, in which the results obtained from instrument trials were also used as data to test hypotheses.

The instrument used as a variable measurement tool consists of a sibling rivalry scale, namely the sibling rivalry scale. This measuring instrument is constructed based on the theory Shaffer & Kipp (2014) with aspects of jealousy, revenge, and competition; as well as a psychological well-being scale, namely a psychological well-being scale constructed based on theories Ryff (2014) regarding psychological well-being with six dimensions which include goals in life, self-development, self-acceptance, independence, positive relations with others, and environmental mastery.

The stages in constructing the two measuring instruments carried out by the researcher were based on the basic steps of construction by, Azwar (2021) among others: 1) Identification of Measurement Objectives, selecting a definition, understanding, and recognizing the theoretical basis used to measure the two variables; 2) Limitation of the Domain of Measure, describing the dimensions or aspects of each variable; 3) Operationalization of Dimensions/Aspects, determines the direction of the response to be expressed in the form of a statement and determines the item format concerning the test material, subject conditions, and measurement objectives; 4) Item review, the first item review is carried out by the researcher by reassuring whether the statements prepared are in accordance with the dimensions/aspects used. Furthermore, readability tests were carried out on 5 research subjects and examined the suggestions that had been given so that they were in accordance with the understanding in question. Lastly is a review conducted by three expert judgments which were processed using the Aiken's V formula as a content validity test; 5) Field Test, the measuring instrument that has been prepared is tested on research subjects directly; and 6) Reliability Estimation Item Selection, the score of respondents' answers obtained through the field test is used for item analysis.

The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) method with Jeffrey's Amazing Statistics Program (JASP) 0.17.7 is used for model testing or construct validity testing. Based on the calculation results obtained, it was concluded that the sibling rivalry scale fit model contained 10 items, namely 2 items for jealousy, 4 items for resentment, and 4 items for competition (GFI=0.980; RMSEA=0.074; IFI=0.960 ; CFI=0.959; TLI=0.948; PNFI=0.721; *range loading factor* =0.582–0.769). While the fit model on the psychological well-being scale has 16 items, namely 2 items on the aspect of goals in life, 3 items on the aspect of self-development, 3 items on the aspect of self-acceptance, 2 items on the aspect of independence, 4 items on the aspect of positive relations with others, and 2 items on environmental mastery aspects (GFI=0.989; RMSEA=0.061; IFI=0.944; CFI=0.942; TLI=0.922; PNFI=0.636; *range loading factor* =0.597–0.958). The two measuring instruments are Likert scales with 4 alternative answer choices, namely Very Unsuitable

(STS), Not Appropriate (TS), Appropriate (S), and Very Appropriate (SS). On the favorable item, SS answer choices get a score of 4, S gets a score of 3, TS gets a score of 2, and STS gets a score of 1. Meanwhile on the unfavorable item, SS answer choices get a score of 1, S gets a score of 2, TS gets a score of 3, and STS gets a score of 4.

Figure 3. Sibling competition variable measurement model

Figure 4. Model of psychological welfare variable measurement

Next is construct reliability by calculating *Composite Reliability* (CR) and *Average Variance Extracted* (AVE). Both methods are used to determine internal consistency based on the level of homogeneity of the items in the instrument being measured (Hair dkk., 2019). The CR value rule stated by Hair dkk. (2014) is ≥ 0.7 (*good reliability*). CR values between 0.6 and 0.7 indicate *acceptable reliability*, provided that other indicators of model construct validity meet the requirements. The AVE estimate is used as a measure of internal consistency. According to Hair dkk. (2019), an AVE value of 0.5 or higher indicates adequate convergence. Conversely, $AVE < 0.5$ indicates that the average item has more remaining errors than the variance has together with the latent factors that contain it. The sibling rivalry scale met construct reliability with a CR value of 0.909 and an AVE of 0.5. Likewise with the psychological well-being scale which gets CR values between 0.6 and 0.7 (0.769; 0.816; 0.762; 0.750; 0.795; 0.653) and AVE values > 0.5 (0.6; 0.6; 0.5; 0.6; 0.5; 0.5).

Convergent and Discriminant Validity

The psychological well-being scale is a measuring tool with a multidimensional model. So it is necessary to fulfill convergent and discriminant validity tests. The measuring instrument will meet convergent validity if the loading factor is $AVE \geq 0.5$ and the CR value is ≥ 0.7 and the AVE value is ≥ 0.5 . Based on the CR and AVE obtained, it was concluded that the dimensions of goals in life, self-development, self-acceptance, independence, positive relations with others, and mastery of the environment have met convergent validity.

The requirement for discriminant validity is to compare the AVE with the square of the correlation between the two constructs. According to Fornell & Larcker, if the AVE value is greater than the squared value of the correlation between the constructs, the measuring instrument meets discriminant validity (Ab Hamid dkk., 2017). In the development of the psychological well-being scale measurement tool, it is known that there are 3 dimensions that meet discriminant validity and 3 dimensions that do not meet discriminant validity, namely self-acceptance, positive relations with others, and environmental mastery ($p = 0.517; 0.494; 0.485$; indicates $p < * 0.591$ * squared correlation dimensions of self-acceptance and environmental mastery).

In fulfilling the assumption test, a normality test and a linearity test are carried out. Whereas to test the hypothesis using regression analysis with a significant value <0.05 (Sig. <0.05), which means that there is a role for the independent variable to the dependent variable.

Results

Description of Subject Characteristics

Subject characteristics reported in this study included age, gender, and details of the number of siblings. The most age of the research subjects was 16 years with a percentage of 75.51% and the others were spread over the ages of 14 years (0.68%), 15 years (23.13%) and 17 years (0.68%). Subjects classified as having an age difference of 0-3 years were as many as 33 students (22.45%) and 114 students (77.55%) had an age difference of >3 years with their siblings. Female subjects were more involved in this study with a percentage of 65.31% and the rest were male with a percentage of 34.69%. Details of siblings owned by the respondent are recorded as follows.

Table 1. Characteristics of Subjects based on number of siblings

What order do you come in your family-	Number of siblings	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	1	40	27,21
	2	22	14.97
	3	4	2.72
2	1	36	24,49
	2	19	12.93
	3	5	3,40
	4	1	0.68
	5	1	0.68
3	2	9	6,12
	3	2	1.36
	4	1	0.68
4	3	5	3,40
	4	1	0.68
5	4	1	0.68
Total		147	100

Descriptive Analysis

Sibling rivalry as measured using a sibling rivalry scale for 147 respondents produces the following statistical description.

Table 2. Sibling Rivalry Scale Statistical Description

Variable	N	Hypothetical				Empirical			
		Min	Max	Means	S.D	Min	Max	Means	std. Dev
Sibling Competition	147	10	40	25	5	10	38	19,068	5.50

Based on this table, it can be concluded that sibling competition in grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso gets a minimum score of 10, a maximum score of 40, a mean value of 25, and a standard deviation of 5. In empirical data, a minimum score of 10 is obtained, a maximum score of 38, a mean value of 19.068, and a standard deviation of 5.50. So that the following categorization is obtained.

Table 3. Sibling competition score categorization

	Category	Intervals	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Currently	Low	$X < 20$	75	51,02
		$20 \leq X < 30$	66	44,9
	Tall	$X \geq 30$	6	4,08
Total			147	100

The table above shows that 75 research subjects (51.02%) have sibling rivalry in the low category and have the highest frequency. The remaining 66 research subjects (44.9%) had sibling rivalry in the high category and 6 research subjects (4.08%) had sibling rivalry in the low category. So it can be concluded that the average grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso have sibling competition in the low category.

Psychological well-being variables are measured using a psychological well-being scale to 147 respondents produced statistical descriptions as follows.

Table 4. Statistical description of the psychological well-being scale

Variable	N	Hypothetical				Empirical			
		Min	Max	Means	S.D.	Min	Max	Means	S.D.
Psychological Well-being	147	16	64	40	8	27	60	45,82	6,96

In table 4 it can be concluded that the hypothetical psychological well-being data for 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso get a minimum score of 16, a maximum score of 64, a mean value of 40, and a standard deviation of 8. In empirical data, a minimum score of 27 is obtained, a maximum score of 60, a mean value of 45.82, and a standard deviation of 6.96. So that the following categorization is obtained.

Table 5. Psychological wellbeing score categorization

	Category	Intervals	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Currently	Low	$X < 32$	3	2,04
		$32 \leq X < 48$	87	59,18
	Tall	$X > 48$	57	38,78
Total			147	100

Based on the categorization norms, it shows that the level of psychological well-being of the subjects is spread out as many as 87 research subjects (59.18%) belong to the medium category, 57 research subjects (38.78%) belong to the high category, and 3 research subjects (2.04%) belong to the low category. So it can be concluded that most of the 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso have psychological well-being in the high category.

Psychological well-being has several dimensions, each of which contributes to the level of psychological well-being. When described will produce data as follows.

Table 7. Categorization Based on psychological welfare dimensions

Dimensions	Category	Intervals	Frequenc y	Percentage (%)	Empirical Means	Hypothet ical Means
Goals in life	Low	$X < 4$	29	19.73	5.91	5
	Currently	$4 \leq X < 6$	72	48.98		
	Tall	$X > 6$	46	31,29		
Self- development	Low	$X < 6$	39	26,53	7,93	7,5
	Currently	$6 \leq X < 9$	52	35,37		
	Tall	$X > 9$	56	38,10		
Accepting yourself	Low	$X < 6$	23	15.65	8.59	7,5
	Currently	$6 \leq X < 9$	43	29,25		
	Tall	$X > 9$	81	55,10		
independence	Low	$X < 4$	54	36,37	4.93	5
	Currently	$4 \leq X < 6$	43	29,25		
	Tall	$X > 6$	50	34.01		
Positive relations with others	Low	$X < 8$	2	1.36	13,28	10
	Currently	$8 \leq X < 12$	16	10.88		
	Tall	$X > 12$	129	87,76		
Environment al mastery	Low	$X < 4$	39	26,53	5,19	5
	Currently	$4 \leq X < 6$	37	25,17		
	Tall	$X > 6$	71	48,3		

Based on table 7, it can be concluded that the dimensions of goals in life, self- development, self-acceptance, positive relations with others, and environmental mastery have the highest contribution to the level of psychological well-being of the research subjects. While the dimensions of independence of research subjects are low.

Classic assumption test

In this study, the classic assumption test that needs to be fulfilled is the normality test and the linearity test. The calculation of the classical assumption test uses the help of the SPSS 25.0 *for Windows program*. The following are the results and explanations of the classic assumption test.

Table 8. Normality test

Variable	Sig.	Ket.	Conclusion
Sibling Competition and Psychological Well-Being	0.200	Sig. $p > 0.05$	Normal

The normality test is carried out to find out whether the research variables are normally distributed. This study used the *One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov test*. If the significance value of $p > 0.05$, the data is normally distributed. Based on the table above, it can be concluded that the data has a significance value of 0.200 which indicates that the research data is normally distributed.

Table 9. Linearity test

Variable	Significance	Conclusion
Sibling Competition - Psychological Well-Being	<i>Deviation of Linearity</i> <i>Linearity</i>	Sig. $p > 0.05$ Sig. $p < 0.05$

The linearity test on research data aims to find out whether the independent variable has a linear relationship with

the dependent variable. Research data will be said to be linear if it has a significance value of *Deviation from Linearity* $p > 0.05$ and a significance value of linearity $p < 0.05$. In this research data has a significance value of *Deviation from Linearity* of 0.521 and *linearity* of 0.05×10^{-4} which indicates that the two variables have a linear relationship.

Hypothesis testing

To prove the hypothesis in this study using regression analysis with the help of the SPSS 25.0 *for windows program*. Based on the calculations that have been done, the following results are obtained

Table 10 . Regression Analysis

Variable	R	p.s	R Square	Unstd. Coeff	Conclusion
Sibling Competition (X) and Psychological Wellbeing (Y) *	-0.370	0.04×10^{-4}	0.137	54,743 -0.467	Hypothesis Accepted

The regression analysis hypothesis can be accepted if the significance value is < 0.05 . Based on this table, it is known that the results of the regression analysis obtained are 0.04×10^{-4} ($\text{sign} < 0.05$) . The regression equation obtained is Psychological Welfare= $54.743 - 0.467$ Sibling Rivalry, which means that every increase in sibling rivalry by 1 unit will decrease psychological well-being by 0.467. Sibling rivalry contributes 13.7% to the level of psychological well-being. So it can be concluded that there is a role of sibling competition on psychological well-being in 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso .

Discussion

This study shows that the level of sibling rivalry is in the low category. Based on these results, it can be interpreted that grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso show a low level of jealousy, competition, and hatred that is formed in their siblings . The form of relationship that exists on the subject can be more inclined to warmth, relative strength, or conflict (Buhrmester & Furman, 1990). The low occurrence of jealousy, revenge, and competition against siblings in the subject, indicates a good handling.

Ecological Theory by Urie Bronfenbrenner states that the environmental system is the basis for the influence of a development (Santrock, 2019b). One of the things that can be a factor in the low sibling rivalry is how parents as the child's closest environment respond to or anticipate this happening to children. According to Scharf dkk. (2005) and (Jensen dkk., 2023) the factors that influence the level of sibling rivalry is how the quality of the role of parents towards children is formed. Hurlock (2011) also stated that the parenting style adopted by parents had a role in sibling rivalry in the family. This is also supported by research (Panggabean, 2021) which states that the way parents educate their children shows a significant relationship. Basically, the family is the first place for children to develop and it is possible for children to learn something starting from how it happened in their family environment.

In this case, the role of parents is very important to help manage competition between siblings (Novairi & Bayu, in Parwati & Koiri, 2019). Parents must ensure that no child feels neglected or unfair, and provide equal opportunities for each child in terms of praise, appreciation, and parents should also promote cooperation and help children solve problems constructively. This can help foster a sense of teamwork and cooperation, while allowing each sibling to feel valued and supported.

In addition, the form of communication that exists within the scope of sibling relationships can also be a factor in the level of sibling rivalry. Rakhmat (2021) argues that good relationships can be formed with the quality of good interpersonal communication, not the quantity of communication. Research Kurniawan & Vionald (2021) shows that the form of parental communication is an important factor in the occurrence of sibling rivalry. If the child shows several attitudes that lead to sibling rivalry and does not get good directions or explanations, it will tend to foster sibling

rivalry in the child.

The characteristics of research subjects who have a higher percentage of age difference > 3 years is also a factor why the level of sibling competition in subjects is low. Research has Buckles & Munnich (2012) shown that children with an age difference of 1-3 years increase the likelihood of sibling rivalry. Parents' attention to siblings with a fairly close age difference can be interpreted as "favoritism" if the child misunderstands the meaning of this (Woolfson, 2004). Based on research McHale dkk. (2012), parents need to avoid the perception of "favorite child" so that good relationships are established between siblings and teaching is needed regarding techniques to reduce conflict from an early age.

The level of psychological well-being of the subject which shows an average in the high category indicates that the subject has a tendency towards good life goals, is able to carry out self-development, has good self-acceptance, is independent, has positive relationships with others, and is able to master the environment. One of the factors that supports the high level of psychological well-being is age (Ryff & Keyes, 1995). The age of the research subjects was more widely distributed in the age range of 15-16 years than the younger age. According to Ryff's research (in Fitri dkk., 2017), the older the age, the higher the level of psychological well-being. Research by Supriyadi dkk. (2020) also shows that the level of psychological well-being in adolescents will increase with age.

Based on the results of the categorization of each dimension of psychological well-being, it is known that the dimension that gives the highest contribution to the level of psychological well-being of 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso is positive relations with other people. At this time, teenagers spend more time with their friends (Santrock, 2019a). This is because teenagers have more active time when they are at school and learn many things from their closest circle, namely the circle of friends. Positive relationships that are formed within the circle of friends have a positive impact on the formation of assertive behavior that can support adolescent life satisfaction (Pebrianty, 2021). Life satisfaction is an indicator that the individual's psychological well-being is well formed (Akhtar, 2009).

Independence is the lowest contributor to the level of psychological well-being of research subjects. According to Allen & Joseph (in Santrock, 2019a) adolescent independence will be more mature if teenagers are able to explore a wider social world than in childhood. Grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso are native residents of Bondowoso district or are not immigrants. This could be a factor why the independence dimension The subject of this research is low. According to Erikson (in Desmita, 2017) independence is obtained in the process of searching for ego identity, for example, trying to break away from parents, where previously all decisions were the obligation of parents to choose. Now in their teens they are expected to be responsible for themselves. However, this responsibility can also not be fully formed due to several factors, one of which is the upbringing of parents. This is supported by the results of research studies Soleha dkk. (2023) which show that one of the factors of independence is parenting parents, apart from genes, the school education system, and community life system.

Based on this study, sibling rivalry plays a role in the level of individual psychological well-being. Patalay & Fitzsimons (2018) suggests that psychological well-being in adolescents is measured in how individual satisfaction is from various sides of life, one of which is the family. Sibling rivalry can be one of the things that happens in the family circle. Within this scope, the dynamics of sibling rivalry creates feelings of jealousy, revenge, and competition in adolescents (Shaffer & Kipp, 2014). They can be jealous of parents' attention that they feel is unfair, hold grudges because they are always harmed both verbally and non-verbally, and compete unfairly because they want to prove that one of them is the greatest or feel that they are always being compared to their siblings and then feelings arise. want to beat the opponent.

Jealousy, revenge, and unhealthy competition in adolescents will lead them to negative emotions that cause depression, anxiety, and stress (Sudjiwanati & Pinastikasari, 2022). According to Hurlock (2011) aggressive behavior such as hitting, biting, kicking, injuring, can also appear to beat their opponents, in this case are siblings. Feelings of inferiority in adolescents can also decrease because of their confusion in assessing what is happening in the sibling rivalry

(Parwati & Koiri, 2019). Research by Plamondon dkk. (2021) also shows that there is a link between the emergence of low self-esteem and individual life satisfaction in sibling and family competition, aggressive behavior, and feelings of intimidation that arise. Sibling rivalry that appears also leads individuals to poor academic achievement because there is a role between sibling rivalry and achievement motivation in adolescents (Asari & Suarya, 2019). Things that become the impact of sibling rivalry can interfere with life goals, self-development efforts, self-acceptance, independence, positive relations with others, and environmental mastery of adolescents. So that these things have a role in the level of psychological well-being of adolescents. However, minimal sibling rivalry in adolescents can play a positive role. Adolescents can build adolescent character and social skills such as negotiation, communication, and empathy by starting at home, namely with siblings. Teenagers who are able to handle problems in their relationships well, will direct children to learn about good personality and wisdom (Parwati & Koiri, 2019).

Based on the results obtained in processing this research data, it can be seen that sibling rivalry has a significant role in the level of psychological well-being of students. For students who are involved in sibling competition, the level of psychological well-being tends to be low and vice versa. The role that was found was also proven through previous research which stated that sibling rivalry had a relationship with psychological well-being at different subject levels, namely 153 class VII students of SMPN 12 Semarang, with a psychological well-being regression line = $142.214 - 0.527$ Sibling Rivalry, in 30 (Pertiwi & Frieda, 2018) adolescents aged 12-19 years who have siblings with *Down syndrome* with a correlation value of 0.402 (Fahmi & Handayani, 2018); on children, adolescents, and early adults (Stocker dkk., 2019); and on 356 high school students in West Jakarta with a correlation value of -0.114 (Hasanah & Fitri, 2020). Research on psychological well-being in adolescents is still rare. With this research, the development of a measurement tool for sibling rivalry and psychological well-being is carried out which still has limitations. So that further development is needed for further researchers.

Conclusion

This study has found that sibling rivalry among grade 10 students of SMAN X Bondowoso tends to be low and the psychological well-being level of grade 10 students at SMAN X Bondowoso tends to be high. The results of the hypothesis testing conducted found that sibling rivalry has a role in the psychological well-being of 10th grade students of SMAN X Bondowoso. Regression analysis shows sibling rivalry can reduce psychological well-being. Problems in the family, especially in siblings, cannot be avoided. However, in an effort to fulfill the psychological well-being of adolescents, it is necessary to be able to manage these problems properly. Adolescents' immediate environment also greatly influences adolescents' views of sibling relationships. So it is necessary to pay attention to the internal and external factors of sibling competition in order to create good psychological well-being in adolescents as the basis for the direction of adolescent development.

This study still has limitations on the measuring instrument used, namely the psychological well-being scale. So that future researchers are expected to be able to modify the three dimensions (self-acceptance, positive relations with others, and mastery of the environment) which still do not meet discriminant validity by redefining the form of items that can describe these dimensions so that discriminant validity can be fulfilled.

References

- Ab Hamid, M. R., Sami, W., & Mohmad Sidek, M. H. (2017). Discriminant validity assessment: use of Fornell & Larcker criterion versus HTMT criterion. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 890(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/890/1/012163>
- Akhtar, M. (2009). *Applying positive psychology to alcohol-misusing adolescents a pilot intervention*. [Doctoral dissertation, University of East London]. <https://www.positivepsychologytraining.co.uk/MAPPdissertation.pdf>
- Akhtar, M., & Boniwell, I. (2010). Applying positive psychology to alcohol-misusing adolescents: A group intervention. *Groupwork: An Interdisciplinary Journal for Working with Groups*, 20(3), 6–31. <https://doi.org/10.1921/095182410X576831>
- Asari & Suarya. (2019). Peran kecerdasan emosional dan persaingan antar saudara terhadap motivasi berprestasi pada remaja. *Jurnal Psikologi Udayana*, 6(3), 44-55.
- Azwar, S. (2021). *Penyusunan Skala Psikologi*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.

- Batubara, A. (2017). Hubungan antara religiusitas dengan psychological well being ditinjau dari big five personality pada siswa SMA Negeri 6 Binjai. *Al-Irsyad: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*, 7(1), 48–62.
- Buckles, K. S., & Munnich, E. L. (2012). Birth spacing and sibling outcomes. *Journal of Human Resources*, 47(3), 613-642. <https://doi.org/10.3368/jhr.47.3.613>
- Buhrmester, D., & Furman, W. (1990). Perceptions of sibling relationships during middle childhood and adolescence. *Child Development*, 61(5), 1387-1398. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.1990.tb02869.x>
- Buist, K. L., Deković, M., & Prinzie, P. (2013). Sibling relationship quality and psychopathology of children and adolescents: A meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 33(1), 97-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2012.10.007>
- Desmita. (2017). *Psikologi Perkembangan Peserta Didik*. Jakarta: PT Remaja Rosdakrya.
- Fahmi, U. N., & Handayani, M. M. (2018). Hubungan antara dimensi sibling relationship dengan psychological well-being pada remaja yang mempunyai saudara kandung down syndrome. *Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Perkembangan*, 7, 39–46.
- Fitri, S., Luawo, M. I. R., & Noor, R. (2017). Gambaran kesejahteraan psikologis pada remaja Laki Laki di SMA Negeri Se-Dki Jakarta. *Insight: Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling*, 6(1), 50-59. <https://doi.org/10.21009/insight.061.05>
- Goldstein, S., & Naglieri, Jack. A. (2011). *Encyclopedia of child behavior and development*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79061-9>
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Multivariate data analysis* (7 ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis* (8 ed.). Cengage Learning, EMEA. www.cengage.com/highered
- Hasanah, N., & Fitri, S. (2020). Pengaruh Sibling Relationship Terhadap Kesejahteraan Psikologis Peserta Didik SMA Negeri Jakarta Barat. *Insight: Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling*, 9(2), 166-178. <https://doi.org/10.21009/insight.092.07>
- Hou, X. H., Gong, Z. Q., Wang, L. J., Zhou, Y., & Su, Y. (2020). A reciprocal and dynamic development model for the effects of siblings on children's theory of mind. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.554023>
- Hurlock, E. B. (2011). *Psikologi Perkembangan : Suatu Pendekatan Sepanjang Rentang Kebidupan* Edisi Kelima. Jakarta : Erlangga.
- Jensen, A. C., Killoren, S. E., Campione-Barr, N., Padilla, J., & Chen, B.-B. (2023). Sibling relationships in adolescence and young adulthood in multiple contexts: a critical review. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 40(2), 384–419. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02654075221104188>
- Kurniawan, F., & Vionald, S. D. (2021). Hubungan gaya komunikasi orang tua dengan sibling rivalry pada remaja di desa manalu kecamatan parmonangan kabupaten tapanuli utara. *Journal of Millennial Community*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.24114/jmic.v3i1.25539>
- Laeque, S. H., Saeed, M. A., & Bilal, A. (2022). Psychological mechanisms linking sibling abuse and school delinquency: an experiential sampling study based on conservation of resources theory. *Motivation and Emotion*, 46(2), 197-210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-022-09925-6>
- Mami, L., & Suharnan. (2015). Harga diri, dukungan sosial dan psychological well being perempuan dewasa yang masih lajang. *Persona: Jurnal Psikologi Indonesia*, 4(3), 216– 224.
- Masuroh, & Ramadhana, R. N. (2016). Hubungan sibling rivalry dengan penyesuaian sosial pada anak usia 11 – 12 tahun di SD 02 Genuk Ungaran Kabupaten Semarang. *Jurnal Kebidanan*, 8(2), 140-150. <https://doi.org/10.35872/jurkeb.v8i02.215>
- McHale, S. M., Updegraff, K. A., & Whiteman, S. D. (2012). Sibling Relationships and Influences in Childhood and Adolescence. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 74(5), 913-930. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-3737.2012.01011.x>
- Muqhniiy, C. K., & Amna, Z. (2016). Perbedaan Psychological Well-Being Pada Remaja Obesitas Dengan Remaja Yang Memiliki Berat Badan Normal. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Psikologi*, 1(3), 52-61.
- Murray, A. L., Zhu, X., Mirman, J. H., Ribeaud, D., & Eisner, M. (2021). An Evaluation of Dual Systems Theories of Adolescent Delinquency in a Normative Longitudinal Cohort Study of Youth. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 50(7), 1293-1307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-021-01433-z>
- Na'imah, T., & Tanireja, T. (2017). Student Well-being pada Remaja Jawa. *Psikohumaniora: Jurnal Penelitian Psikologi*, 2(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.21580/pjpp.v2i1.979>
- Panggabean, S. M. U. (2021). Hubungan Pola Asuh Orang Tua terhadap Kejadian Sibling Rivalry pada Anak di RW 002 Kelurahan Bukit Tempayan Kecamatan Batu Aji Kota Batam. *Jurnal Surya Medika*, 6(2), 155-161. <https://doi.org/10.33084/jsm.v6i2.2133>
- Papamichail, A., & Bates, E. A. (2022). "I Want My Mum to Know That I Am a Good Guy ...": A Thematic Analysis of the Accounts of Adolescents Who Exhibit Child-to-Parent Violence in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(9–10), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520926317>
- Parwati, N., & Koiri, M. (2019). Sibling Rivalry As Reflected In Julie Anne Peters' Luna. *Litera Kultura*, 7(4).
- Patalay, P., & Fitzsimons, E. (2018). Development and predictors of mental ill-health and wellbeing from childhood to adolescence. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 53(12), 1311-1323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-018-1604-0>
- Pebrianty. (2021). Relasi Sosial Dan Dampaknya Pada Global Life Atisfaction Remaja Di Wilayah Karisidenan Kediri [Conference

- Presentation]. *Prosiding Seminar Hasil Penelitian Tahun 2020: Diseminasi Hasil Penelitian Untuk Meningkatkan Kesehatan*, 147–156. IIKBW PRESS.
- Pertiwi, R. G., & Frieda, N. (2018). Hubungan antara sibling rivalry dengan psychological well-being pada siswa kelas VII SMP Negeri 12 Semarang. *Jurnal Empati*, 7(4), 1298-1306. <https://doi.org/10.14710/empati.2018.23437>
- Plamondon, A., Bouchard, G., & Lachance-Grzela, M. (2021). Family Dynamics and Young Adults' Well-Being: The Mediating Role of Sibling Bullying. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 36, 9-10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518800313>
- Prabowo, A. (2016). Kesejahteraan Psikologis Remaja di Sekolah. *Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi Terapan*, 4(2), 246-260. <https://doi.org/10.22219/jipt.v4i2.3527>
- Rakhmat, J. (2021). *Psikologi Komunikasi* (Edisi Revisi). Simbiosis Rekatama Media. 21
- Ramadhani, T., Djunaedi, D., & Sismiati S., A. (2016). Kesejahteraan psikologis (psychological well being) siswa yang orangtuanya bercerai (studi deskriptif yang dilakukan pada siswa di SMK Negeri 26 Pembangunan Jakarta). *Insight: Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling*, 5(1), 108. <https://doi.org/10.21009/INSIGHT.051.16>
- Ryff, C. D. (2014). Psychological well-being revisited: Advances in the science and practice of eudaimonia. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*, 83(1), 10–28. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000353263>
- Ryff, C. D., & Keyes, C. L. M. (1995). The structure of psychological well-being revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719–727. <https://doi.org/10.1037/00223514.69.4.719>
- Santrock, J. W. (2019a). *Adolescence* (17 ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Santrock, J. W. (2019b). *Life-span Development* (17 ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Sarafino, E. P., & Smith, T. W. (2017). *Health Psychology (Biopsychosocial Interactions)*. In John Wiley's & Sons Inc (9th ed.). Wiley.
- Scharf, M., Shulman, S., & Avigad-Spitz, L. (2005). Sibling Relationships in Emerging Adulthood and in Adolescence. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 20(1), 64–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0743558404271133>
- Shaffer, D. R., & Kipp, K. (2014). *Developmental Psychology: Childhood and Adolescence* (9 ed.). Cengage Learning. www.cengage.com/highered
- Soleha, A., Nelyahardi, & Amanah, S. (2023). Faktor Kemandirian Siswa untuk Menentukan Bidang Studi Lintas Minat di SMA Negeri 4 Kota Jambi. *Journal on Education*, 5(3), 10095–10104. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i3.1899>
- Stocker, C. M., Gilligan, M., Klopach, E. T., Conger, K. J., Lanthier, R. P., Nepl, T. K., O'Neal, C. W., & Wickrama, K. A. S. (2019). Sibling Relationships in Older Adulthood: Links With Loneliness and Well-Being. *Journal of Family Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/fam0000586>
- Sudjiwanati, & Pinastikasari, N. (2022). Sibling Rivalry and Aggressive Behaviour on Stress Towards The 5.0 Community Era. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2022(4), 11379–11387. <http://journalppw.com>
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Jakarta: Alfabeta.
- Supriyadi, S., Saifudin, I. M. Moh. Y., & Hartono, B. (2020). Faktor-Faktor Yang Berhubungan Dengan Psychological Well-Being Remaja SMP Negeri 1 Banguntapan Bantul Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Perawat Indonesia*, 4(3), 437-445. <https://doi.org/10.32584/jpi.v4i3.635>
- Tangdilintin, A. F. (2019). Remaja Dan Media Sosial. *Cura Animarum*, 1(1), 1-6.
- VandenBos, G. R. (2015). *APA dictionary of psychology* (2nd ed.). (2 ed.). American Psychological Association (APA). <https://doi.org/10.1037/14646-000.22>
- Wells, I. E. (2010). *Psychological well being psychology of emotions motivations and action*. In Nova Science Publisher, Inc (Vol. 5, Nomor 3).
- Woolfson, R. C. (2004). *Persaingan Saudara Kandung: Mendorong Anak-anak untuk menjadi Bersabab*. Jakarta: Erlangga.

